

INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF INVESTMENT IN BANKS

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes the factors affecting the investment activity of commercial banks of Uzbekistan and the volume of their investment credit flows. In order to develop the investment activities of banks, recommendations on using the experience of foreign countries have been developed.*

***Key words:** banking system, bank deposits, investment loan, syndicated loan, investment project, interest rate, inflation.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in the period of instability in the world economy, it is an important issue to develop the economy of our country and increase its level of competitiveness. For this, it is necessary to deepen structural changes in the economy, develop high-tech production, modernize industrial sectors, and accelerate the process of technological renewal. It was not without reason that the President of our country emphasized that "in the implementation of our planned program in the near future, the modernization of our economy and its leading industries, the acceleration of technical and technological renewal and its expansion, and the diversification of production should take a central place." In order to positively solve these issues, it is necessary to develop the investment activities of commercial banks, which are the main investment institutions in our country.

Investment activity of banks is related to the activity of the bank, as an investor, in order to acquire financial assets, create and organize real assets, and place funds. The investment activity of banks differs from the activity of other investors in that

they carry out the investment against the funds involved. That is why, on the one hand, the bank appears in the market as an investor, and on the other hand, it is a debtor. This situation makes liquidity an important issue for banks, which require proportionate management of assets and liabilities in terms of maturity, size and interest rates.

In developed countries, the main source of financing the investment activities of commercial banks is time and savings deposits attracted from customers. This is because, firstly, capital is a relatively expensive form of financing the activities of commercial banks;

secondly, according to the nature of the activity of commercial banks, they are commercial organizations engaged in attracting temporary free funds of residents and enterprises to deposit accounts and placing them in the form of loans and investments;

thirdly, interbank loans are a relatively expensive financial resource, therefore, their use in financing asset operations leads to an increase in the amount of interest expenses of commercial banks;

fourth, commercial banks do not have the right to use transaction deposits directly, that is, without concluding a term deposit agreement

Direct use of transaction deposits as a resource by commercial banks in transition economy countries, that is, without concluding a term deposit agreement, has a negative effect on the strength of their deposit base and contributes to the increase in liquidity risk. This is because the transaction deposit is a passive one with a very high level of volatility. It can be requested by the customer at any time. Therefore, in the banking practices of developed countries, transaction deposits are not considered a source of resources for a commercial bank, and interest is not paid to them.

In the resource base of banks of developed countries, customers' funds occupy a high weight. In particular, in Finland, Italy, more than 30% of the total bank

liabilities correspond to the funds of clients (including individuals). This figure is 80% in Japan and Israel.

Due to the development of the financial market in developed countries, the funds received from the sale of securities issued by commercial banks are the total amount of their resources.

occupies a significantly higher share in volume. These resources are mainly used to finance long-term investment operations of banks.

Investments in securities are an important component of investment activity in banking practices of developed countries. Investments made by banks in securities are 16.2% in French commercial banks, 15.5% in Germany, 23.8% in Italy, 7.8% in Great Britain, 23.8% in Spain, 2.2% in the USA, In Belgium - 6.4%, in Japan - 10.2%.

Due to the insufficient development of the financial market in our republic, commercial banks participate in the financing of investments mainly with long-term loans. Bank loans for more than one year are considered long-term loans, and they are given for the purpose of financing the investment costs of the population and economic entities.

METHODS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The weight of Uzbek banks' investments in real assets is high. For example, the volume of investment loans allocated by commercial banks for modernization, technological and technical re-equipment of enterprises amounted to 5.7 trillion soums. In the last 3 years, the volume of such loans has increased by 2.2 times. The share of long-term loans in the total loan portfolio of banks is 76.8%. These data show that the investment activities of our country's banks are developing.

It is necessary to analyze the term of the loans in order to assess the qualitative changes occurring in the structure of the credit investments allocated to the economy by the commercial banks of our country. Long-term loans make up 76.8% of the loan portfolio of our republic's banks. This situation indicates, firstly, that the

lending activities of commercial banks are increasingly developing; secondly, it shows the active involvement of banks in the process of financing investment projects; thirdly, it indicates the increasing demand of commercial banks for loans of the population and economic entities for financing investments.

Factors such as the refinancing rate of the Central Bank, mandatory norms for deposit interest rates, interest rates on long-term loans, and the inflation rate affect the amount of investment loans of commercial banks of our republic.

During 2012-2022, the weighted average annual interest rate on long-term loans decreased from 18.5 to 12.2. This shows that it is cheap to use bank loans for financing investment projects of enterprises.

Inflation also affects the volume of investment loans. In the conditions of high inflation, the investment activity of banks decreases, because the interest rate of loans increases and the interest of banks to engage in speculative operations increases. The higher the inflation rate, the lower the real interest rate of banks, which does not encourage banks to invest. During the next 5 years in our republic, the level of inflation was around 7-8 percent, which led to a decrease in interest rates on bank loans.

The reduction of interest rates of long-term loans, changes and differentiation of mandatory reserve rates played an important role in the high growth rate of credit deposits of commercial banks of our republic. However, among the factors affecting the volume of investment loans of commercial banks, it is necessary to emphasize the level of economic development of the regions, the cost of resources, and the presence of state incentives for commercial banks.

The capacity of commercial banks to provide investment loans is primarily determined by the adequacy of their resource base. The first part of the resource base of commercial banks of our country consists of capital, and the second part consists of deposits. In recent years, commercial banks have had a tendency to increase both capital bases and deposit bases.

It is worth noting that, although deposits in commercial banks of our republic have a general growth trend, their base should be further strengthened at the expense of long-term deposits. Because the share of transaction deposits in the total volume of deposits in commercial banks of our republic remains above 50 percent. According to experts of the World Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the share of transaction deposits in total deposits should not exceed 30 percent. Otherwise, there will be a shortage of term funds, and this will limit the increase in lending capacity of commercial banks.

The second important component of the resource base of commercial banks is their capital base. According to the international model developed by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, the capital of commercial banks consists of core and additional capital, where the core capital consists of stable financing sources. Therefore, the main capital of commercial banks is an important and stable source of financing investment loans.

According to the recommendation of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, the requirement for regulatory capital adequacy is set at 8 percent, and from January 1, 2019, it is set at 10.5 percent, taking into account the minimum requirement for special reserve capital. At the end of 2022, the level of capital adequacy of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 24.3 percent, which is 3 times higher than the accepted international norm.

Commercial banks of our republic increase their capital by issuing additional shares. During 2012-2022, the issuance of additional shares of commercial banks of our republic increased from 247.7 billion soums to 500 billion soums or 2 times. This situation, firstly, serves to increase the level of capitalization of commercial banks, and secondly, serves to further develop their investment activity. It also means that the interest in shares of commercial banks is growing from year to year, and the activity of banks in the securities market is increasing.

As a result of the measures taken to further expand the stable resource base in

banks, the volume of certificates of deposit issued and placed by commercial banks increased by 1.6 times over the next 3 years to 445.6 billion soums, and the volume of long-term bonds increased by 1.5 times to 258.7 reached a billion soums.

Commercial banks, on the one hand, attract funds by placing their own securities, i.e., shares, bonds, and certificates of deposit, on the stock market, and on the other hand, they purchase various securities from this market and place their investments.

Commercial banks of our country should pay special attention to the profitability ratio of securities when investing. Their level being at least the refinancing rate (12%) is a moderate condition for increasing the bank's income and maintaining its liquidity.

When making investments, banks should pay attention not only to profitability, but also to the level of liquidity of the bank. In order to finance investment projects, they should finance long-term investment loans at the expense of their own capital and long-term deposits. Only then the bank will not have a liquidity problem. Also, banks should increase the quality of expertise of investment projects and open credit lines for real effective projects. However, there are also unprofitable investment projects due to the fact that there is no demand for their products, they are not exported or they are exported in very small quantities, enterprises do not work at the capacity specified in the project, and they are not provided with enough raw materials, or their activities depend on foreign raw materials. depends. As a result, the loans taken for financing the investment project and their interest are not returned on time. If these loans are taken in foreign currency, it will be difficult for companies to repay them due to exchange rate changes. That is why it is advisable for banks to improve the quality of expertise of investment projects, to involve international experts in the expertise of large and complex projects. In particular, it is appropriate for these foreign banks to participate in the expertise of projects financed through foreign bank credit lines.

The main part of the investment activity of the banks of the developed countries corresponds to the contribution of the practice of granting syndicated loans. In our country, commercial banks should also widen the practice of syndicated lending, which will develop their investment activity and improve its management. Because in this, a number of banks participate together in the financing and management of large projects, risks are shared and resources are pooled. Also, the economic regulations established by the Central Bank regarding the lending activities of commercial banks will not be violated.

It is necessary to implement the financing of large investment projects by issuing syndicated loans together with banks of foreign countries. This reduces the level of risk associated with the financing of projects and makes it possible to study foreign experience in their expertise.

Banks in our republic should actively attract funds from various off-budget funds and insurance companies to finance investment projects in economic sectors. Because most of these funds are long-term, their transformation into financing of investment projects does not cause liquidity problems in banks. Also, it is appropriate to provide the funds of the Recovery and Development Fund of Uzbekistan, which has accumulated a large amount of financial resources in the form of foreign currency, to commercial banks in the form of subordinated debt for financing effective investment projects.

Most of the economic entities operating in the regions of our country are small enterprises, and one of the main factors preventing them from using bank loans to finance their investment projects is the issue of supply. In order to positively solve this, first of all, commercial banks should increase the volume of leasing operations in order to finance the investment activities of enterprises. Secondly, it is necessary to quickly establish a loan guarantee fund in our republic, taking into account the world experience and our national characteristics.

It is necessary to use foreign experience in order to protect the population's savings in banks from devaluation as a result of inflation. For example, Chilean banks are mandated to set a "floating" interest rate above the real inflation rate rather than a fixed rate on deposits. Also, to increase the attractiveness of deposits for the population, raising their rates by increasing their duration will strengthen the stable resource base of banks. As a result, the investment opportunities of banks will expand.

CONCLUSION

In short, the implementation of the measures proposed above will develop the investment activity of commercial banks and have a positive effect on the stable growth of our economy.

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